

The Study of Postcolonial Consciousness through Selected poems of A. K. Ramanujan

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Abstract:

Writings of the diaspora occupy an important place in Indian literature. It provides a conceptual framework and defines positions where a new identity is constructed that negotiate the limits and concerns of various metaphors of time and space. The diaspora writers 'most profound sympathies and attachments are to their country and they view India as their true home. India, its culture and people have been shown by these Indian writings in English. A representative of Indian English poetry, A.K Ramanujan is a prominent voice of the Indian Diaspora. His poems exhibit an Indian and western mind, where he stresses the need to incorporate the practical and meaningful aspects of tradition into modernity. His sensitivities are rooted in his Indian inheritance, but he evidently has a modernist vision. The poems of Ramanujan reflect upon the transcendental essence of traditional Hindu meditations, his memories, the sentimental nostalgia, the appeal of mythical and archetypal symbols, and his sense of belongingness to his native homeland. This paper aims to analyse how he synthesizes the diverse cross-cultural confrontation between the traditional east and the modern west in his poetry.

Keywords: Post-Colonialism, Cultural Identity, Hybridity, Memory, Tradition, Modernity.

Among the most influential among the modern Indian poets who wrote in the modernist post- independence phase is A.K. Ramanujan (1929- 1993.) He is bilingual, having written both in his native Kannada and English. A volume of his poetry, titled Selected Poems, was released by the Oxford University Press in 1976. He was awarded the Padma Shri Award in 1976 and was also elected Fellow of the American Academy of Fine Arts and Sciences. A.K Ramanujan's poetry shows both a command of diction and a voice of authenticity. Ramanujan doesn't indulge in mere philosophical presentation or partake in socio-political notions; his art represents an unusual sensitivity to life reality. Furthermore, his poems present the intercultural experience of the

synthesis between the east and the west. His collections The Striders (1966), Relations (1971) and Second Sight (1987) illustrate his expanding horizons with an increasing understanding of the self. His fame rests not only a reputable poet, but also an internationally renowned translator. His translations of the classics of Tamil and Kannada reflect beauty and elegance and approach the originals most closely via their subtle evoking. Ramanujan is among the writers of the Indian diaspora during the last decade who have been on centre stage, mainly due to the theoretical formulations created by their work and increasing contribution to cultural studies. Their writing raises questions about what it means to be at home and how we define our identities. Likewise,

Ramanujan's poetry stems from his simultaneous devotion to two separate modes of interpretation—the traditional and the unavoidable modern. He acknowledges the influence of traditional Tamil and Kannada poetry from the Middle Ages on his poetic mind and language. His poetry is turned into an arena where the need to connect to history through tradition clashes with contemporary truth and immediacy. In his poetry, family life, rural India, culture, and its superstitions, the landscape of India serves as subjects. He looks at the gradual decline of an old tradition and recognizes the manner the modern society is still attempting to hold on to.

The main focus of his creativity is on the decline of his own tradition. At the same time, there is a struggle for self, cultural identity, personal relationships with regard to existential issues of who we are and where we come from. He received his legacy of traditional and modern thinking from his father. His mother gave him a good sense of cultural identity and local community. The house of Ramanujan in Mysore is an important part in the personal landscape of the poet. It is a vibrant place with numerous streams of languages and perspectives. His father lived on the second floor of the building, and if he went upstairs, he would converse with him in English. He would converse in Tamil with his mother in the kitchen and in Kannada outside on the streets, which is why he identified English as the upstairs language and Tamil and Kannada as the downstairs languages. In the words of Ramanujan, English and my discipline (Linguistics and Anthropology) give me my outer forms - linguistic, metrical, logical and other such ways of shaping experience and my first thirty years in India, my frequent visits and field trips, my personal and professional preoccupations with Kannada, Tamil, the classics and folklore give me my substance, my 'inner' forms, images and

symbols. They are continuous with each other and I no longer can tell what comes from where. (Parathasarathy 95) The difficulty of most Indo-English poets is said to be the vulnerability of language alienation from English as an innovative expressive medium. As Raja Rao says, —One has to convey in a language that is not one's own. One has to convey the various shades and missions of certain thought movement that looks maltreated in an alien language (vi). However, as K.R.S. Iyengar puts, —what makes Indo-Anglian literature an Indian literature, and not just a ramshackle outhouse of English literature, is the quality of its —Indianness— in the choice of subject, in the texture of thought and play of sentiment, in the organization of material, and in the creative use of language (Mohan xvii).

Ramanujan certainly is a subject of ethnic ambivalence and cultural complexities, yet he did not naturalize western themes and customs like the Indian ones. His "Indianness" is an enticing source of charm for him as it has been striking and powerful. This special sense of expression of A.K. Ramanujan makes him an influential voice among his contemporaries. He is rooted in Indian Territory, Indian culture, rituals, myths and traditions. The poetry of Ramanujan represents a touch of Indian ethos and his English poetry is cultural, literary and assimilates Indian cultural characteristics. For example, in his "Small Scale Reflections on a Great House" he engages the Western paradigm in an allegedly Indian existence. He combines the styles of India and Europe in new ways and handles, adapts and assimilates other beliefs and cultures without losing consciousness of being an Indian. Bruce King says: "He showed that Indian poets could both be modern and work from within their own literary traditions" (Modern Indian Poetry in English 36).

Ramanujan is a representative of a new kind of poetry that emerged in English in the mid-

20th century by poets like Parthasarathy, Kolatkar, Kamala Das that studied the foundations of their own society and culture and made social and religious reforms. In sensitivity and content, it was Indian, but its language was English. This mode of expression wherein writing of these Indian writers had its roots and its stems in the Indian environment, but in the English language is as a type of hybridity. Homi Bhabha in his *Location of Culture* introduced the 'hybridity' concept to describe the culture and identity construction under colonial power structures and inequality. Hybridity is, for him, the mechanism by which the colonial government undertakes to transform the colonized identity into a singular one (the other) into a universal structure, but doesn't often develop familiar aspects. According to him, Hybridity is the intermediate space between where hegemonic colonial cultural narratives are disrupted and displaced. This intermediate space is also called the 'third space'. There are several modes of hybridization: linguistic, culture, political, ethnic, etc. Hybridity represents an "intermediate" state of a human being between two cultures in literary contexts. One of the challenges of postcolonial literature, especially for writers living in foreign lands, is figuring out how to integrate and articulate the various cultural influences on a writer in other ways than a solely thematic approach.

Although some authors have taken over, post-modernism's open forms allow for the juxtaposition of opposing concepts, passages influenced by various languages and cultures. Ramanujan's poetry is an example of a more refined, elegant, and profound style of writing

with multi-cultural aspects. As an expatriate, Ramanujan has used his experience to confront the ideals of the motherland, India, and the United States of America. His poetry gives us intricate descriptions of childhood memories and events and focuses on the emotional experiences of people in Indian and Western societies. He tries to look back to the westernized culture and establish their lost identity and negotiates various boundaries of time and space by employing various approaches. Ramanujan lived at the crossroads of two worlds – his inner and intimate world of which lied in the memories of his memories in India and the new identity and outlook of the outside world of his residence.

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